

Editor in Chief

**Dr Adebayo Ola
AFOLARANMI**

Department of Religious
and Intercultural Studies,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Editors

**Assoc. Prof Adekunle
Olusola OTUNLA**

Department of Mass
Communication and Media
Technology,
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

**Dr Michael
GBADEGESIN**

Department of Languages
and Literature
Lead City University,
Ibadan, Nigeria

Associate Editors

**Dr Emmanuel O.
MALOMO**

ECWA Gospel Centre,
Kano, Nigeria

**Rebecca Oluwatosin
BANJO**

Department of Peace
Studies and Conflicts
Resolution, Ajayi Crowther
University, Oyo, Nigeria

**Emmanuel Selome
FASINU**

Department of Political
Science, Wesley University,
Ondo, Nigeria

© 2025 Authors

**Home-Related Factors as Determinant of
Academic Achievement in Social Studies
among Junior Secondary School Students
in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo
State, Nigeria**

Fausat Olawumi OLADIMEJI

*Department of Arts and Social Science Education,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*
olawumio470@gmail.com

Yejide Adepeju IBIKUNLE, PhD

*Department of Arts and Social Science Education,
Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria*
ibikunlevejide@gmail.com

Abstract

This study examined the influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of JSS II students in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State. A total of 1,114 male and female students from 13 public secondary schools in the local government made up the population. A sample size of 104 students was determined using a multistage sampling procedure. The descriptive survey research design was employed. Data were collected using both a self-developed questionnaire and a Social Studies academic achievement test, with a cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.89 and a KR-20 coefficient of 0.82, respectively, which confirmed the reliability of the instruments. Data was analysed using frequency, percentage, chi-square, and multiple regression at $p < 0.05$. The results showed that the level of academic achievement of junior secondary school students' Social Studies students was high (38.5%), level of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies was also high (Mean=3.28), there was no statistically significant

influence of Home-related factors on the academic achievement of the students [parent occupation ($p=0.867$), parent education ($p=0.560$), and parental involvement ($p=0.304$)]. The study concluded that home-related factors have a limited influence on junior secondary school students' academic achievement in Social Studies. It was recommended among others that teachers should sustain the high achievement by using effective teaching methods and adequate instructional materials.

Keywords: Home-related Factors, parent occupation, parent education, parental involvement, and Academic Achievement in Social Studies

Introduction

Education continues to be a vital tool for social cohesion, human capital development, and national development, especially at the basic school level when students gain the fundamental civic, social, and cognitive skills. Academic achievement or performance is a key factor in determining students' learning outcomes and the effectiveness of educational institutions in any given system. Academic achievement demonstrates how well students understand, apply, and retain knowledge across a range of subjects (Sievertsen et al., 2022). Standardized tests, classroom evaluations, examinations, and overall grades are just a few of the tools frequently used by teachers and schools to gauge students' academic achievements (Nanyonjo, 2025). According to Dosunmu and Adetayo (2021), high academic achievement not only indicates a student's mastery of the subject matter but also the presence of encouraging and conducive learning settings both at home and at school. This is because both settings have a significant impact on the caliber of instruction students receive and how involved they are in class. This suggests that students are less likely to do well academically when households and schools do not provide sufficient learning resources, facilities, or a supportive environment for instruction. Given that academic achievement is impacted by both environmental and instructional elements, attention must be paid to subjects that integrate cognitive and social development.

Since it aims to foster civic engagement, social awareness, moral values, and a knowledge of societal relationships, Social Studies holds a prominent place in the junior secondary school curriculum of the Nigerian educational system. The subject was created in 2007 by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) with the goal of fostering civic engagement, cultural sensitivity, and citizenship. Social Studies integrates

Economics, Geography, Sociology, Government, and History to promote a comprehensive grasp of society's existence (Unimna et al., 2020). According to Gbadamosi (2013), the basic goals of the Social Studies curriculum which includes knowledge, skills, values, and civic engagement are designed with the Nigerian environment in mind, a view also supported by a recent finding (Bishara & Gidado, 2024)). As a result, student academic achievement is directly related to the effectiveness of Social Studies instruction and serves as a key measure of how well the goals of the subject are being met.

Even though Social Studies is important for both individual and societal growth, junior secondary school students in many public schools in Nigeria continue to perform poorly academically in the subject. Numerous elements that contribute to this academic underachievement have been identified by research undertaken in Nigeria. These include unsatisfactory learning settings, low student engagement, a lack of parental involvement, and issues relating to school, like inadequate technology and textbooks, underqualified teachers, and restricted access to educational materials. These elements also contribute to students' disinterest and lack of desire, which prolongs their scholastic difficulties in Social Studies (Elujekwute, 2021).

Given that low Social Studies performance might erode students' civic competency, value orientation, and preparedness to participate positively in society challenges, this ongoing trend has alarmed educators and policymakers. In this context, academic achievement is a reflection of students' intellectual prowess as well as the combined impact of various environmental and psychosocial factors that influence learning outcomes.

While school-related factors such as teacher quality, instructional strategies, and the availability of learning resources are unquestionably important, research on determinants of academic achievement has traditionally focused on these factors, often ignoring the home environment, which is a child's first and most permanent context for learning and socialization. It is where socioeconomic circumstances start to have an impact and where fundamental attitudes regarding education are formed. The home is crucial in forming students' attitudes toward education, study habits, motivation, discipline, and exposure to academic support, all of which have a direct impact on academic achievement (Okeke & Okoli, 2022).

Home-related characteristics are multifaceted, and in educational research, parental involvement, parental education, and parental occupation have

emerged as particularly important indicators. The educational background of parents may affect their ability to set reasonable educational expectations, promote learning, and offer academic guidance. Steinmayr et al. (2014) reported that higher parental education is often linked to better home learning settings, more effective communication with teachers and schools, and increased support for children's academic endeavors, according to empirical data. Additionally, parental education affects attitudes toward learning, parenting styles, and techniques of discipline, all of which have a major impact on students' academic achievement (Steinmayr et al., 2014). On the other hand, parental occupation frequently reflects socioeconomic circumstances that impact time available for overseeing schooling, stability of the home environment, and access to educational resources. According to Osaro-Martins et al. (2024), there is a strong positive relationship between students' academic achievement and their parents' occupational standing, particularly in foundational courses such as Social Studies and Language. Moreover, students' engagement and dedication to academic duties are further reinforced by parental involvement, which includes keeping an eye on academic activities, corresponding with teachers, and promoting learning at home. Compared to students without such support, those whose parents are actively involved in their education typically do better and behave more consistently in the classroom (Owoeye et al., 2022). Omaliko & Okpala (2021) reported that stable families and family sizes have a positive impact on students' academic performance. Also, Kabilito (2024) agreed that parental involvement and the home environment are significant predictors of cognitive aptitude in a variety of subjects.

Although previous research has looked at these home-related aspects, a lot of them have done so separately, producing inconsistent results that do not fully represent their overall impact on students' academic achievement. Furthermore, there are not many context-specific research that use these variables in Oyo State's rural and semi-urban local government districts. There is currently little empirical data on how parental educational attainment, occupational patterns, and involvement levels all affect students' academic achievement in Social Studies in the Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area. In light of this, the current study aims to investigate the influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in social studies among in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the significance of Social Studies in fostering civic engagement, social responsibility, and national consciousness, students' academic achievement in the subject is still routinely low. The impact of the home environment, which is crucial in determining students' attitudes, motivation, and study habits, has received relatively little and uneven attention, compared to several studies on school-related aspects that influence students' performance. Current empirical research on home-related factors typically looks at parental involvement, education, or occupation separately, which leaves an incomplete picture of how these factors work together to influence students' academic achievement. There is a glaring absence of comprehensive data regarding how these home-related factors collectively impact students' academic achievement in Social Studies within the Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area. To fill this gap, this study investigates the influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in social studies among in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to investigate the influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in social studies among in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State. The objectives of the study were to:

1. examine the level of academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State.
2. examine the level of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State
3. ascertain the influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State

Research Questions

1. What is the level of academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State?

-
2. What is the level of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There will be no significant influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State

Methodology

This study used a descriptive survey research design, which involved collecting data from a representative sample of the population to generate findings that could be generalized to the study's population. The population comprised all students in public junior secondary schools in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State. At the time the study was conducted, there were 13 public secondary schools with a JSS II student population of 1,114. The sample size was determined using a multistage sampling procedure. First, a purposive sampling technique was employed to select Ajaawa Township as the study area because it comprises both urban and rural communities, offering a diverse socio-cultural and educational context for comparative analysis. Next, all 13 public secondary schools in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area were identified as the sampling frame. Convenient sampling method was used to select eight (8) JSS II students from each school to ensure representation across schools while maintaining manageable class-based groupings, which is the baseline. Using this procedure, an appropriate sample size of 104 students was established.

Two instruments were used for data collection: a self-developed four-point Likert-scale questionnaire titled the Home Factor Questionnaire (HFQ) and the Social Studies Academic Achievement Test (SSAAT). The questionnaire was structured into sections. Section A consists of the demographic information of respondents. Section B consists of items that assess home factors such as parental education, parent occupation, and parental involvement. The Social Studies Academic Achievement Test consists of 20 multiple-choice questions, each with four options (A–D), designed to measure students' knowledge, understanding, and application of Social Studies concepts taught at the Junior Secondary School II level. The

questions were adopted from the approved Social Studies curriculum for JSS II students, focusing on core content areas such as citizenship education, values, socialization, social institutions, peace and conflict, and governance.

The reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach's Alpha and the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20), which produced a coefficient of $\alpha = 0.89$ for the questionnaire and a reliability coefficient of 0.82 for the Social Studies Academic Achievement Test, indicating a high level of internal consistency. Ethical principles guiding data collection, analysis, and reporting, as prescribed by Lead City University, were strictly observed throughout the study. Data were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, and mean scores were used to answer the research questions, while simple regression analysis was employed to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Presentation of Demographic Data

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Age (Years)		
10-12	21	20.2
13-15	77	74.0
16 and above	6	5.8
Gender		
Male	46	44.2
Female	58	55.8
Father's Occupation		
Farming	28	26.8
Trading	39	37.5
Civil Servant	23	22.1
Artisan	14	13.5
Unemployed	0	0.0
Mother's Occupation		

Farming	23	22.1
Trading	44	42.3
Civil Servant	25	24.0
Artisan	10	9.6
Unemployed	2	1.9
Father's Level of Education		
No Formal Education	7	6.7
Primary	25	24.0
Secondary	43	41.3
Tertiary	29	27.9
Mother's Level of Education		
No Formal Education	11	10.6
Primary	15	14.4
Secondary	48	46.2
Tertiary	29	27.9
Vocational Skills	1	1.0
Total	104	100

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 shows that 58 (55.8%) respondents were female, while 46 (44.2%) were male, indicating a higher female students' participation in the study. Regarding age, the study had more respondents, 77 (74.0%), between the ages of 13-15 years, 20 (20.2) respondents between the ages of 10-12 years, and 6 (5.8) respondents aged 16 years and above. The students' parents engaged more in trading as their occupation than in other occupations, having 44 (42.3%) mothers and 39 (37.5%) fathers who are traders. The table also shows secondary school as the highest level of education of 48 (46.2%) mothers and 43 (41.3%) fathers of the study's participants.

Presentation of Answers to Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the level of academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Table 2: Level of Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School II Students in Social Studies

Level of Academic Achievement	Frequency	Percent
Less than 40 Marks	31	29.8
40-69 Marks	33	31.7
70-100 Marks	40	38.5
Total	104	100

Source: Researchers’ Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 reveals that 40 (38.5%) students fall into the high-level category, 33 (31.7%) students fall into the moderate level category, and 31 (29.8%) students fall into the low-level category of academic achievement. Overall, the result suggests that the level of academic achievement of Junior Secondary School II students in Social Studies is high, indicating that most students possess a satisfactory understanding and mastery of the subject content.

Research Question Two: What is level of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State?

Table 3: Level of Home-Related Factors on Students Academic Achievement

Statements	SA (%)	A (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std.
Parental Education						
My parents’ level of education positively influences my academic performance.	63 (60.6)	32 (30.8)	6 (5.8)	3 (2.9)	3.49	0.73
My parents set high expectations for my academic performance.	51 (49.0)	32 (30.8)	12 (11.5)	9 (8.7)	3.20	0.95

Weighted Mean = 3.35						
Parental Occupation						
My parents' occupation provides adequate financial support for my schooling needs.	50 (48.1)	42 (40.4)	7 (6.7)	5 (4.8)	3.32	0.80
I have access to textbooks and learning	48 (46.2)	34 (32.7)	13 (12.5)	9 (8.7)	3.16	0.95
My parents reward me when I perform well in school.	48 (46.2)	35 (33.7)	16 (15.4)	5 (4.8)	3.21	0.87
Weighted Mean = 3.23						
Parental Involvement						
My parents supervise my homework regularly.	65 (62.5)	27 (26.0)	8 (7.7)	4 (3.8)	3.47	0.79
My parents encourage me to study Social Studies at home.	48 (46.2)	40 (38.5)	11 (10.6)	5 (4.8)	3.25	0.83
My parents discuss my academic progress with my teachers.	49 (47.1)	38 (36.5)	8 (7.7)	9 (8.7)	3.22	0.92
I receive moral support from my parents when I face academic challenges.	59 (56.7)	27 (26.0)	11 (10.6)	7 (6.7)	3.32	0.91
My parents provide a conducive reading environment at home.	46 (44.2)	36 (34.6)	17 (16.3)	5 (4.8)	3.18	0.87
My parents attend school meetings to discuss my progress.	54 (51.9)	31 (29.8)	15 (14.4)	4 (3.8)	3.30	0.85
I don't often have time to read at home because of too much house chores.	45 (43.3)	30 (28.8)	21 (20.2)	8 (7.7)	3.07	0.97
Weighted Mean = 3.26						
Overall Weighted Mean = 3.28 (High)						

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Key: SA- Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), Disagree (1)

Decision Rule: Mean value of ≥ 3.00 (High), 2.5-2.99 (Moderate), ≤ 2.5 (Low)

The result on Table 3 reveals an overall weighted mean score of 3.28 which indicates a high influence of home-related factors (parents' education, parent occupation, and parental involvement) on students' academic achievement in Social Studies. 63(60.6%) respondents strongly agreed that their parents' level of education positively influences their academic achievement. 65(62.5%) respondents strongly agreed that their parents supervised their home-work regularly, while 59(56.7%) respondents strongly agreed that they receive moral support from their parents when faced with academic challenges. However, only 51 (49%) respondents strongly agreed that their parents set high expectations for their academic performance. Just 48 (46.2%) respondents have access to textbooks, learning, and are encouraged to study Social Studies at home. 46 (44.2%) respondents strongly agreed that they are provided with a conducive home environment for reading, and 45 (43.3%) exchange study time at home for house chores.

Test of Hypothesis

***H₀₁*:** There will be no significant influence of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State

Table 4: Summary of Regression Analysis of the Influence of Home-Related Factors on the Academic Achievement of Junior Secondary School Students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Beta	t	d
				.
				E
				r
				r
				o
				r

(Constant)	12.874	4		3.043	0.003
		.			
		2			
		3			
		1			
Parental Occupation	0.114	0	0.016	0.167	0.867
		.			
		6			
		8			
		0			
Parental Education	0.403	0	0.059	0.585	0.560
		.			
		6			
		8			
		8			
Parental Involvement	-0.149	0	-0.154	-1.034	0.304
		.			
		1			
		4			
		4			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, 2025

Table 4 reveals the influence of home-related factors: parent occupation, parent education, and parental involvement on students' academic achievement in Social Studies, using Multiple Regression analysis. Parent occupation ($\beta = 0.016$, $p = 0.867$), parent education ($\beta = 0.059$, $p = 0.560$), and parental involvement ($\beta = -0.154$, $p = 0.304$) did not show a relatively significant influence on junior secondary school students' academic achievement in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the first research question revealed a high level of academic achievement in Social Studies among junior secondary school students of Ogo-Oluwa Local Government, Oyo State. This result implies that a good number of the students possess a satisfactory understanding and mastery of the subject content, and can most likely apply this knowledge in their everyday lives. However, the level of academic achievement can be attributed to a combination of variables besides home-related factors (Anagaw et al, 2024).

Research question two findings showed that the level of home-related factors on the academic achievement of Junior Secondary School students in Social Studies in Ogo-Oluwa Local Government Area of Oyo State was high. The finding is strongly supported by several studies. Research conducted in Osun State revealed that several home variables significantly predict students' achievement in Social Studies, showing that factors within the family environment directly affect performance in the subject (Adeyemi, 2016). This suggests that the home plays a foundational role in shaping students' understanding and success in Social Studies.

The findings of the hypothesis revealed that the indices of home factors (parent education, parental involvement, and parent occupation) do not have a statistically significant influence on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in Social Studies. The findings suggest that students' academic achievement in Social Studies is apparently less dependent on parental background characteristics, but could be a result of a mix of other factors, such as students' study routine, the teaching skills of Social Studies teachers, or the availability of instructional materials in schools. In the Nigerian context, Okonkwo and Eze (2020) also observed that factors such as peer relationships and student engagement can sometimes outweigh traditional home-based predictors like parental education or occupation. Regardless of their educational or occupational background, parents should continue to create supportive home environments for learning, encourage positive study habits, and maintain communication with teachers (Boi, 2020). This reinforces the notion that parental encouragement and emotional support can be just as important as formal education or socioeconomic status in shaping students' attitudes toward learning (Okonkwo & Eze, 2020).

Conclusion

The study found that junior secondary school students in Ogo-Oluwa LGA, Oyo State recorded a high level of academic achievement in Social Studies, suggesting satisfactory understanding of the subject. Home-related factors were also rated high, indicating that the home environment generally supports learning. However, hypothesis testing showed that parental education, parental involvement, and parental occupation did not significantly influence students' achievement. This implies that students' performance may depend more on other factors such as study habits, peer

influence, teacher effectiveness, and availability of instructional materials. Nevertheless, parents should continue to provide encouragement and a supportive home environment to strengthen students' learning outcomes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the study's findings;

1. Teachers should sustain the high achievement by using effective teaching methods and adequate instructional materials.
2. Parents should maintain strong home support by providing a conducive study environment and monitoring students' study routines.
3. Schools should strengthen other influencing factors by improving guidance/counselling, encouraging positive peer learning, and ensuring learning resources are available to all students.

References

- Adeyemi, B. A. (2016). Home variables as predictor of students' achievements in social studies in junior secondary schools in Osun State, Nigeria. *Asian Social Science, 12*(3).
- Anagaw, E. M., Sharew, I. A., & Mossu, F. Y. (2024). Impact of teaching quality on student achievement: Student evidence. *Frontiers in Education, 9*.
- Bishara, A. A., & Gidado, B. K. (2024). Social studies curriculum as an instrument for enhancing social stability and national development in a democratic Nigeria. *Benin Journal of Educational Studies, 29*(1–2), 165–170.
- Boi, P. B. L. (2020). *The influence of home environment on learning achievements among students in public day secondary schools in Mbulu Town Council, Tanzania* (Unpublished master's thesis). University of Dodoma.
- Dosunmu, M. M., & Adetayo, J. O. (2021). Subjective wellbeing and cognitive test anxiety as predictors of students' academic achievement in business-related subjects. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies, 24*(1), 363–373.
- Elujekwute, E. C., Shir, J. N., Nnome, C. I., & Elujekwute, L. A. (2021). Influence of home and school environments on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Nigeria. *Sapientia Foundation Journal of Education, Sciences and Gender Studies, 3*(3), 209–226.
- Gbadamosi, V. (2013). Effects of teaching citizenship component of social studies on primary school pupils' civic knowledge and skills. *Nigerian Journal of Social Studies, 16*(2).
- Kabilito, I. J. (2024). The influence of instructional materials on students' academic achievement. *Research Invention Journal of Law, Communication and Languages, 3*(2), 30–33.

- Nanyonjo, S. (2025). The role of standardized testing in public education. *Eurasian Experiment Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 6(3), 102–109.
- Okeke, A. F., & Okoli, C. R. (2022). Influence of home background on academic performance of secondary school students in English language in Anaocha Local Government Area of Anambra State. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 5(1).
- Okonkwo, D., & Eze, J. (2020). Parental involvement and student academic performance in public secondary schools in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 8(3), 99–118.
- Omaliko, E. L., & Okpala, E. N. (2021). Influence of teachers' qualifications on academic performance of students in mathematics. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 5(3), 39–46.
- Osaro-Martins, B., Olaofe, A., Shogbesan, Y., Abdulazeez, B., & Yusuff, A. (2024). Socioeconomic status of parents and academic performance of students in senior secondary school in Alimosho Local Government of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Evaluation Studies in Social Sciences*, 5(2), 34–48.
- Owoeye, O., Faleye, B., & Jimoh, K. (2022). Student factors and parental involvement on academic performance of senior secondary school students' qualifying examination in Osun State secondary schools. *Journal of Digital Learning and Education*, 2, 127–133.
- Sievertsen, H. H., Terrier, C., & Bolotnyy, V. (2022). *Assessments in education: Academic achievement and student outcomes* (arXiv preprint).
- Steinmayr, R., Meißner, A., Weidinger, A., & Wirthwein, L. (2014). Academic achievement. In *Oxford bibliographies in psychology*. Oxford University Press.
- Unimna, F. A., Essien, E. E., Effiom, V. N., & Ele, B. G. (2020). Examining social studies curriculum in Nigeria among global realities: Issues, challenges and the way forward. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 156(2), 145–159.